

BUS SAFETY MONITORING SYSTEM DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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Abstract. As the pandemic occurred, everything we used to do has changed dramatically from face-to-face in school to online class learning and working in offices or establishments to working from home now. It also affected public transportation where people used it for their daily lives going to their work and schools to reach their target destination. Public utility buses also apprehend their operation to help reduce the transmission of the virus from one place to another place using a public utility bus. When the operation started again, the DILG announced that no more medical certificates and travel authorities were needed to travel using the buses from one place to another. According to the study, the transmission of the virus can also be done via public transportation. Based on the observation and gathered information, the proponents found out that the passengers who ride the bus for their public transportation experience some safety protocols that are not correctly performed. The scenario may lead to transmission of the virus because of the overloading of the bus, which breaks the protocol of social distancing. No proper or minor checking of the body temperature of the passengers entering the bus may let the virus carrier enter the bus and spread the virus—a manual collection of the passenger's necessary information in case of contact tracing. The stakeholder has a lack of safety protocols against the coronavirus in their public transportation. These problems often lead to a chance of spreading the virus on the bus among all passengers. This proposed project for public utility buses may help the stakeholders reduce the probability of spreading the virus on the buses used for public transportation from one place to another.

Keywords. Safety Monitoring System, Public Transport Safety, COVID-19 Pandemic. Monitoring

1 Introduction

As the pandemic occurred, our everyday situation and the things we do have changed instantly. It had given way for change to take its dominion. All aspects of our lives have become different from how they used to—from face-to-face in school to online class learning and working in offices or establishments to working from home now. And we can't deny that even transportation right now has changed. The total seating capacity for passengers in tricycles, jeepneys, or buses has decreased to half. Every ride highlights risks, for there is an interaction with random people with unidentified histories (Nazario, B., MD, September 2020). In this instance, other people's history of travel and activities is not in our hands. On March 1, 2021, the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) announced no need for requirements such as travel authority issued by the Philippine National Police (PNP) and a medical certificate from the LGU Health office traveling public transport. The said mandate is also known as Resolution No. 101 (Chavez, 2021). According to Oxford Academic, the Covid-19 viruses transmission process can also be done or occur in public transportation (Kaiwei Luo, Shixiong Hu, 2020)

Some existing solutions like scanning body temperature before entering malls, markets, churches, schools, and other establishments require this process. Even the need to monitor a vehicle's location through a global positioning system or GPS is implemented. These things still have a lot of space for upgrading and innovating to be more valuable and advantageous for future situations. In public transportation, we all know that there's no proper checking of the person's body temperature entering a public utility vehicle and maintaining the exact capacity of a public utility bus which may lead to overloading the passenger inside the public utility bus. This situation can be solved by innovating and integrating a solution to a specific problem.

The proponents came up with integrating the body temperature using an open-source electronic platform and temperature sensor to scan the passenger's body temperature that will ride on the bus. If the temperature scanner scanned the average temperature, the LCD would display a checkmark together with one beep sound. On the other hand, if it is above moderate or above normal, the LCD will display an "X" mark with a 2-second continuous beep, which will not be allowed to enter the bus. The body temperature will be displayed on the LCD after every scanning. After being scanned,

the counter will start to count for the bus passenger's capacity using the IR proximity sensor upon entering the bus. Moreover, because there is also an instance that even the bus already has its capacity limit, the driver still insists on adding passengers despite reaching or even exceeding the vehicle's required seating capacity. The buzzer will also indicate if the bus already has its seating capacity limit. The capacity counter of the bus can be configurable by the bus operator on the web application they were using. The bus will have a GPS module included in the system. For gathering necessary information about the bus passengers, a QR code will be used to scan the passengers and fill up the form. In case of the absence of a passenger's smartphone for scanning the QR code, a backup smartphone will be provided for them to scan the QR code. All data gathered, such as the passenger's temperature, bus capacity, and the bus location will be sent to the web application using the WIFI module connected to the Internet, used by the bus operator who manages the company. They can monitor and check the bus capacity, and passengers' temperature and determine if the drivers and passengers follow the safety protocol precautions. Also, the bus operator can configure the capacity limit of a particular bus in a web application. Soon, those data can be used for future data analysis like contact tracing, and they can also monitor the bus with its position on the map.

The proposal project still has space for improvements and upgrades that can also be useful for future situations. The proponent's motivation in developing this project is to contribute and help the community prevent the spread of the coronavirus that can be transmitted on public transportation, where people may have different travel and interaction histories. It will also be used for other contact tracings in case of positivity of coronavirus in a person.

2 Review of Related Literature

The start of the pandemic also marked the boosting of changes in human lives. As the pandemic prolonged, more and more aspects were affected, including the inevitable part of everyone's lifestyle, which is transportation. Transportation underlines more than just the risk of road accidents and acquiring a virus, even just by calmly sitting in a vehicle. Since the virus can't be seen, the essential and best approach to this dilemma is to control the environment of transportation through all the commuters by thermal scanning the passengers' body temperature (Evan, 2020). At the same time, counting the number who enter the bus to follow the set number of the bus capacity will be filled (Zerda, 2020). COVID-19 might spread or be transmitted between people mostly when an infected person has close contact with another person, through the person's mouth or nose in small liquid particles when the person sneeze, speak, or cough (Kerkhove, 2020). One-third of the netizens or people in some cities have stopped using public transportation because of the COVID-19 pandemic (Fleming, 2021). But now that the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) confirmed the upon traveling, travel authority and medical certificates from local health offices like LGU are no longer required for traveling (Chavez, 2021). But with the right measures and proper precautions, public transportation can be COVID - safe for all passengers, primarily those who use public utility vehicles, specifically, the bus (Minda, 2020).

There are many things to do to be safe from the coronavirus known as COVID-19. Wearing a facemask, or face shield, bringing own alcohol, maintaining proper social and physical distancing, and mostly in public places like schools, malls, establishments, churches, etc. (WHO, 2020b). One of the best things to do is perform a temperature scanning for every person entering a particular place. Scanning the person's temperature is one thing to do to detect an increased deep body temperature which means that the person has a fever, -- one of the leading symptoms of COVID-19 (Goodwin, 2020). This procedure of safety precaution can be done anywhere, where a place may contain a lot of people like malls, churches, schools, establishments, or markets. The proponents would use an MLX90614 infrared thermal sensor connected to an electronic platform called Arduino which can be programmed using Arduino IDE (Integrated Development Environment). The module is a contactless infrared digital temperature sensor that ranges from -20 °C to 120°C, and it would be used for non-contact temperature measurement. Using a thermal scanner may give accuracy in detecting if a person is infected with the coronavirus, mainly when a person is symptomatic or a person infected with coronavirus has a fever. According to doctors, a temperature of 100.4°F or 38 °C is considered a fever (Goodwin, 2020).

The project would be set to a temperature of 37.2°C for every person entering the bus. A person that has 37.2°C and below temperature is allowed to enter the bus, on the other side, those who are 37.2°C and above are not allowed to enter because this means the person has a fever, where we all know that it is the top one symptoms of coronavirus (Nazario, 2021). For the body temperature limit on buses, if a passenger's body temperature is below the threshold value, which is 37.2°C, a suitable temperature for a person's normal condition, the buzzer will beep just once with a checkmark that will be displayed in an LCD to indicate that the person has an average temperature. On the other hand, if the passenger's body

temperature is above the threshold value, which is 37.3°C and above, the buzzer will beep continuously for 2 seconds together with an "X" mark to indicate that the passenger might have a fever which will not be allowed to enter the bus for the safety of others. However, they can still scan one more time because it can affect the environment's temperature, mainly if exposed to the sun.

It has been almost a year since the operation of public utility buses stopped after the lockdown occurred. However, even though the functions stopped, some provide services wherein the person can ride with others in a car going from provinces to Manila or vice versa. But this service does not follow any physical and social distancing because they are completing the 100% total capacity of the vehicles, which must not. But on February 28, 2021, the Department of the Interior and Local Government (DILG) confirmed that travel authority and a medical certificate would no longer be required for travel – issued Resolution No. 101 (Chavez, 2021). Some areas have their travel restrictions and requirements, mainly for those places with high coronavirus cases. In some places in Pangasinan, there is a coronavirus case because of the people traveling from other areas to the province without knowing that they are infected.

Every public transportation or public utility vehicle, such as tricycles, jeepneys, private cars, and buses, decreased their 100% capacity to 50% to maintain proper physical and social distancing. But this precaution led to the driver's sigh because of small incomes that don't fit and are not enough for their daily lives, primarily because they have their own family to feed. 50% of passenger capacity vehicles, the Department of Transportation (DOTr) implemented a proposal from the National Economic and Development Authority (NEDA) to increase the passenger capacity of public vehicles from 50 percent to 75 percent (Dela Cruz, 2021a). But on March 29, 2021, DOTr Undersecretary Artemio Tuazon said that there would be no change in passenger capacity (Dela Cruz, 2021b). Following the proper accommodation of a public utility vehicle will significantly slow down the transmission and spread. Most probable, physical and social distancing is also strictly followed. One way to make sure that the proper capacity of a vehicle is strictly followed is to have an appropriate counter of capacity. There are projects created in other countries for trains that will count the number of passengers entering the train using a camera located at the vehicle's doorway (Symonds, 2020). Having a capacity counter will help the community lessen the spread of coronavirus from one place to another place. So, the proponent's project is combined with a capacity counter that works to count the passengers who enter the bus. An infrared proximity sensor will be used to detect objects or obstacles in front of the sensor. Two IR proximity sensors will be needed to see the passengers entering the bus and exiting the bus. It will work by having a 1 and 0 process. Whenever each of them first detects an obstacle, it will be the one to work, and the other will not, for its proper function. The proponents use an IR proximity sensor instead of a PIR sensor because IR proximity sensors are a one-way detection that detects if obstacles block the set distance.

In comparison, the PIR sensor is for detecting movements in a wide range of degrees which can affect the counting of passengers. Every number of passengers who enter the bus and the number of passengers left to be filled will be displayed on an LCD. The proposed project will be programmable for setting the correct number of the capacity of the bus, showing in the LCD (liquid crystal display) for example from 42, including the bus driver and the conductor, every person that will enter the bus the number will decrease until it reaches zero (0). Maintaining proper and exact passengers during a pandemic can lead to a slowdown of rising COVID cases in every place because it also performs physical distancing, which is one of many things to do to limit the spread of coronavirus.

In the blast of the COVID – 19, no one is prepared to face this kind of pandemic that hits the whole world in just the blink of an eye. The transmission and spread of the said virus are from person to person (WHO, 2020b). It can be through contact and droplet transmission due to a lack of social and physical distancing in public places, even in private areas. Airborne transmission is the aerosols or the smaller particles that can be spread through air flows that can last after several minutes (Wilson, 2020). When the transmission begins, the symptoms will appear to be close contact into now a COVID patient. The local government will start the process of contact tracing; it is the process of identifying, assessing, and managing people who are exposed to COVID-19 and should monitor their health for symptoms of COVID-19 (WHO, 2020a).

Through technology, contact tracing can be done more easily using Quick Response Code, also known as QR code (Zhuang, 2020). QR code is just like a barcode at the supermarket. Still, this kind of code is an image that can be scanned by any smartphone today with a QR Code reader application and translated into something like a website, application, or any other form (Pagin, 2017). On September 4, 2020, New Zealand proposed to use QR codes for contact tracing on public

transport due to the rapidly increasing COVID-19 cases in their country (Pearce, 2020). In the Philippines, in some provinces like Davao, the Provincial Government of Davao Oriental set to implement the Davao Oriental Digital Contact Tracing System (DAVOR – DCTS). That will require all residents and non – residents to present their QR codes when transacting with various private and public establishments in the province (Miranda, 2021). The proponent will use a QR code scan by the passengers of public utility buses traveling from one place to another. QR code is already in use by others for contact tracing. Still, it can be a great help for the bus company to monitor and keep a record of information to process contact tracing in this field of public transportation. Upon scanning the QR code, the passengers will be directed to a website with a form to be filled up with the passenger's basic information, like their name, gender, age, address, and contact number (CDC, 2020). The process of contact tracing will have a significant impact on the community for breaking the chains of transmission of coronavirus and is one of the essential public health too for controlling infectious disease outbreaks such as COVID-19 in certain places.

3 Project Design and Methodology

To develop the proposed project, a bus safety monitoring system during the COVID-19 pandemic, the proponents would be using an open-source electronic platform with built-in Wi-Fi, thermal scanner, IR proximity sensor, buzzer, GPS module, and LCD Display. The Open-source Electronic Platform would act as the microcontroller that can be programmed, and this is where all the modules would be connected. The thermal scanner is the module used for scanning the passenger's body temperature. Upon scanning the body temperature, The LCD would display a checkmark with a one-beep sound to indicate that the passenger has a normal body temperature which is 37.2 and below. On the other hand, if the passenger has a temperature of 37.3 and above, the LCD would display an "X" mark together with a two-second continuous beep. After determining the passenger's body temperature, the IR proximity sensor would act as the bus's capacity counter to ensure that the passenger's set number is strictly followed upon entering the bus and shows it in the decrement process, and it would also be used for triggering the thermal scanner to scan.

A QR code needs to be scanned by the passengers to enter their basic information, but in case of the absence of the passenger's smartphone, a backup smartphone would be provided for them to scan the QR code and get their necessary information. The GPS module would be the one to send their locations on the map that can be used for tracking and monitoring the site of the bus. The LCD would display the passengers' scanned body temperature before entering the bus. The passenger counts would also be displayed to show the allowed number of passengers who can only enter the bus. Lastly, all data and information gathered would be sent to the web application that the company would use to monitor their buses' location on the map and its information. Also, the bus operator can configure the capacity limit of a particular bus in a web application.

Figure 1. Operational Framework for the Proposed Project

4 Results and Discussion

Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of a wiring layout of the bus safety monitoring system during the covid-19 pandemic. This wireframe contains wirings of the modules and sensors of the project to the brain of the system, which is the Nodemcu. These modules and sensors are the body temperature scanner module, IR proximity sensor, LCD, piezo buzzer, and GPS module with the Nodemcu ESP 8266 with its baseboard. All of these modules and sensors would function using the Nodemcu. The proponents decided to use Nodemcu ESP 8266 instead of Arduino Uno or Arduino Mega and Wi-Fi module because Nodemcu ESP 8266 has built-in Wi-Fi that is needed for sending the data and information to the web application. The Nodemcu must be connected to the Wi-Fi of the bus so that the data will be sent. The Nodemcu was plugged into the Nodemcu baseboard. This baseboard makes the Nodemcu have more input and output pins, especially since some module was used in the project has four pins, such as the LCD, which has 16 pins but converted into four pins using the I2C module, MLX90614 thermal scanner, and the GPS module.

Figure 2 shows the schematic diagram of the possible wirings of the project connected to the battery of the bus. Since the project would only need a power supply, the bus battery is the only thing needed. The battery of the bus is 12v, so the proponents used a step-down/upconverter to supply 5v to the microcontroller. With the use of a switch and fuse, it would help to maintain a connection and disconnection of the power supply

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of the Project to the Bus Battery

The hardware part of the project is the modules, sensors, and the brain of the system, which is the Nodemcu. This Nodemcu is an open-source platform based on ESP8266 which means that this board has a built-in Wi-Fi that lets the data be transferred or sent using the Wi-Fi protocol. This would hold the codes and program of the sensors and modules for them to function according to the needed requirements. The thermal scanner will scan continuously once it is turned on, so the proponents added an infrared proximity sensor that will act as the trigger of the thermal scanner to scan once the sensor detects an object. For counting the capacity of the bus, the proponents used two infrared proximity sensors that will detect a person who will enter the bus and leave the bus.

For displaying the number of capacities of the bus and the temperature that is being scanned by the thermal scanner, the proponents used two pieces of a 16x2 LCD which has 16 pins all in all, but the proponents encountered a problem with the number of pins that contrary to the number of pins of Nodemcu baseboard, so the proponents used an I2C module that converts I2C serial data to parallel data for the LCD.

For locating the position of the vehicle, the proponents used a GPS module that consists of 4 pins are vcc pin connected to a 3v power supply, a ground pin to the ground, the tx pin to D5, which means it transmits the data while the rx pin is not connected because it doesn't need anything to receive.

or indicator, the proponents used a piezo buzzer for a sound indicator of the thermal body temperature scanner and a capacity counter every time the sensor detects an object. The negative pin is connected to the ground, while the positive pin is connected to D3.

Figure 3. Actual Nodemcu and Module Wiring Connections

After connecting the modules and sensors to the microcontroller (Figure 3), the proponent's design for the bus prototype was put into an actual bus prototype. The proponents started to create the bus prototype with the use of cardboard, Styrofoam, colored papers, and glue (shown in Figure 4), where sensors and modules would be installed.

Figure 4. Actual Nodemcu and Module Wiring Connections

The actual model of a bus prototype in which the modules and sensors are installed in the proper places or positions. The thermal body temperature scanner is installed right before the door of the bus (Figure 5) because, before entering the bus, the passenger must first go through the body temperature scanner to determine if the passenger is allowed or not allowed to enter the bus.

Figure 5. Contact-less Body Temperature Before the Door

Upon entering the bus, the two infrared proximity sensors are installed inside the bus where passengers will pass through. This will count the passengers entering and leaving the bus.

Figure 6. Capacity Counter in the Door

In developing the web application, the proponent used Microsoft Visual Studio Code for coding and developing the application that will be used. Using this programming tool helps the proponents to code with ease because of some extensions such as auto-completing tags and putting color to make it easier to look for some codes. Also, this programming tool supports many languages such as Python, Java, C++, JavaScript, PHP, and more.

To get the necessary information about every passenger who rides the bus, the proponents created a fill-up form (Figure 7) that will ask the passengers for their full name, body temperature scanned by the scanner, date of birth, gender, the address where they live, the destination they will go, and the phone number that can be used to contact them in case of contact tracing

Fillup Form

Address

Destination

Phone Number

All fields are required.

Full Name

Temperature
00.0

Date of Birth

Gender
- Please select -

Next

Thank you for your time!

Please accept our Terms and conditions before Submit

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Figure 7. Fill up the Form for the Passengers

On the other side, the web application that will be used for monitoring, Figure 8, shows the login screen of the main web app before entering the monitoring interface. The admin will be asking for their username and password to be able to log in to make it secure that only authorized persons can log in.

Figure 8, shows the main dashboard for admin users of the bus safety monitoring system web application where the proponents designed it simpler for other users to have a user-friendly experience while using the application. It shows the "Passenger Details," which is the number of passengers who scanned the QR code and filled up the form. In "User Summary" shows the number of operators who are the ones who are on the bus, and the admin those who can access the main web application for monitoring. It also shows the bus name with its plate number, the current capacity of the bus, the names of passengers who filled up the form, and the live location where the user can locate the location of the bus on the map.

Figure 8. Fill up the Form for the Passengers

For monitoring the information of the passengers who filled up the form to get their necessary information, in the “Passengers” tab (Plate 7), the passenger screen was able to show the date when the passenger filled up the form, their name, temperature and contact number that can be used to reach them in case of contact tracing, their address, birth date, gender, and destination of their travel.

In monitoring the location of the bus, through the use of the GPS module, the “Location” tab shown in Figure 9 was able to show also the bus name with plate number, the current capacity of the bus, the live location of the bus, departure, and arrival of the bus on its destination. Upon clicking the “view larger map” clickable text, the user will be directed to the Google map which shows the current location of the bus, which is the current location of the house of the proponent.

Figure 9. Location of the Bus on the Map

Based on the result of the evaluation, ten passengers agreed that the capacity counter limits the overloading of the bus, ten passengers also agreed that the QR code directs the passenger to fill up a form, while 10 of them agreed that the GPS gives the exact location of the bus, then ten passengers agreed that the web application shows the proper information that can be monitor and last, ten passengers agreed that the entire feature of the project is a lot easier and safer than the usual manual method.

The proponents used the total percentage formula to get the average percentage of the survey, where the proponents would divide the number of respondents who answered yes to each question by the number of respondents and then multiply it by 100 to get the total percentage.

In computing the total percentage of the bus drivers and conductors, since both of the respondents have a total number of 2 respondents in each bus driver and conductor, they also answered “yes” to all questions in the evaluation form where the project got an average of 100% for the effectivity and usability of the project. For the passengers, 9 out of 10 passengers answered “yes,” and one passenger answered “no” to the question “Does the thermal scanner give accurate temperature?” and the rest of the questions were answered with “yes.”

Overall, the bus safety monitoring system during the COVID-19 pandemic received a high percentage of “yes” in the survey conducted. Across all six questions, an average of 93.33% of the answer was “yes,” while 6.66% answered “no.” Furthermore, it is recommended that future researchers should improve the capturing of the image to minimize the noise in the background. They should confirm if the noise in the captured image is brought about by the low refresh or frame rate of the screen display.

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The proponent's project provides an easier and safer method than the usual manual method, which is writing the information in the logbook, needing a man to get and scan their body temperature and counter, or sometimes not properly performing capacity counting of the bus.

The proponents conclude that monitoring the real-time capacity of the bus is important, especially the main reason for this feature is to limit the number of passengers and avoid the overloading of the bus that may neglect or disregard the social distancing of every passenger. The proponents conclude that some passengers don't experience proper safety protocols. Also, the proponents encountered that while having a survey for the project, the passengers were just entering the bus instantly without scanning their body temperature and logging some necessary information. Based on the survey conducted where it received a high percentage of effectivity and usability, the proponents conclude that using this project was a bus safety monitoring system during the COVID-19 in public transportation.

The proponent's recommendation to the bus company or any public transportation who wants to install the bus safety monitoring system on their buses must use all present and high-quality IT equipment to avoid untoward circumstances. The admin who monitors the system should have a personal computer to access the web application in their office. Hence, they can use a smartphone, but for a better experience and appearance, it is recommended to use a personal computer or laptop. The proponent's recommendation for future researchers that will conduct a study related to this project should broaden the content, especially since this coronavirus pandemic will end.

References

- Chavez, C. (2021). Travel authority, medical certificate no longer required for travel — DILG. Manila Bulletin. <https://mb.com.ph/2021/02/28/travel-authority-medical-certificate-no-longer-required-for-travel-dilg/>
- CDC. (2020). Key Information to Collect During a Case Interview. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/php/contact-tracing/keyinfo.html>
- Evan, B. (2020). Thermal Detection Monitoring in the Age of COVID-19. CIO ASEAN. <https://www.cio.com/article/3543880/thermal-detection-monitoring-in-the-age-of-covid-19.html>
- Fleming, S. (2021). COVID made many of us avoid public transport - what will it take to get us back on the bus? World Economic Forum. <https://www.weforum.org/agenda/2021/02/public-transport-covid-data/>
- Goodwin, M. (2020). Early symptoms of COVID-19: What you need to know. Medical News Today. <https://www.medicalnewstoday.com/articles/coronavirus-vs-flu>
- Kaiwei Luo, Zhao Lei, Zheng Hai, Shanliang Xiao, Jia Rui, Hao Yang, Xinping Jing, Hui Wang, Zhengshen Xie, Ping Luo, Wanying Li, Qiao Li, Hui Lu Tan, Zicheng Xu, Yang Yang, Shixiong Hu, T. C. (2020). Transmission of SARS-CoV-2 in Public Transportation Vehicles: A Case Study in Hunan Province, China. Oxford Academic. <https://academic.oup.com/ofid/article/7/10/ofaa430/5905033>
- Kerkhove, M. Van. (2020). How does COVID-19 spread between people? World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/question-and-answers-hub/q-a-detail/coronavirus-disease-covid-19-how-is-it-transmitted>
- Minda, A. (2020). Five ways to stay safe on public transport during the COVID-19 pandemic. Travel Daily News International. <https://www.traveldailynews.com/post/five-ways-to-staying-safe-on-publictransport-during-the-covid-19-pandemic>
- Miranda, J. (2021). The Philippine province is set to use a QR code system for COVID-19 contact tracing. Open Gov. <https://opengovasia.com/philippine-province-set-to-use-qr-code-system-for-covid-19-contact-tracing/>
- Nazario, B. (2021). Symptoms of Coronavirus. WebMD. <https://www.webmd.com/lung/covid-19-symptoms#1>
- Pagin, S. (2017). QR Codes: What Are They And How Do They Work? Creative Marketing Fast Print. <https://www.fastprint.co.uk/blog/quick-response-codes-what-are-they-and-how-do-they-work.html>
- Pearce, C. (2020). New Zealand uses QR codes for contact tracing on public transport. RailExpress <https://www.railexpress.com.au/new-zealand-using-qr-codes-for-contact-tracing-on-public-transport/>
- WHO. (2020a). Coronavirus disease (COVID-19): Contact tracing. World Health Organization. <https://www.who.int/news-room/q-a-detail/coronavirus-disease-covid-19-contacttracing#:~:text=Yes%2C%20when%20systematically%20applied,as%20COVID-19.>
- WHO. (2020b). Rational use of personal protective equipment for coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) –Interim guidance. WHO Interim Guidance, 2019(February), 1–7. https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/331215/WHO-2019-nCov-IPCPPE_use-020.1-eng.pdf
- WHO. (2020c). Transmission of SARS-CoV-2: implications for infection prevention precautions. World Health Organization. [https://www.who.int/news-room/commentaries/detail/transmission-of-sars-cov-2-implications-for-infection-prevention-precautions#:~:text=Current evidence suggests that SARS breaks chains of transmission.](https://www.who.int/news-room/commentaries/detail/transmission-of-sars-cov-2-implications-for-infection-prevention-precautions#:~:text=Current%20evidence%20suggests%20that%20SARS%20breaks%20chains%20of%20transmission.)

Wilson, N. (2020). Airborne transmission of covid-19. The BMJ. <https://www.bmj.com/content/370/bmj.m3206.short>

Zerda, D. (2020). REAL-TIME OCCUPANCY MONITORING COVID-19 SAFETY MEASURES. SMS StoreTraffic. <https://storetraffic.com/crowd-management-social-distancing/>

Zhuang, I. N. ; S. W. ; Y. G. ; W. (2020). A QR Code-Based Contact Tracing Framework for Sustainable Containment of COVID-19: Evaluation of an Approach to Assist the Return to Normal Activity. JMIR Publications. <https://mhealth.jmir.org/2020/9/e22321>